

THE ROLE OF CASE STUDY TECHNOLOGY IN CRIMINAL LAW EDUCATION

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Abstract

The article discusses the issues of the role of case study technology in the education of criminal law. Its role in pedagogical education has been studied.

Key words: Case study, technology, criminal law, students, lecture, teacher, innovation

In today's modern conditions, building the future of our country through the use of innovative technological achievements in world pedagogy is becoming an important factor of development. During the rapid development of our country observed in recent years, there is a great need for experts who think critically, master information and communication technologies, create and implement innovations. This situation requires the development of programs that help to increase quality indicators in education by introducing innovations, modern interactive and creative teaching methods, support of pedagogical research.

A new education system based on world experience is being established in Uzbekistan. The Law "On Education" adopted on September 23, 2020 provides the legal basis for this. Significant changes are also taking place in the theory and methodology of education and training. In education, a capable layer that can work with new information is being formed. Behaviors focused on the individualization of educational programs are increasing and new creative solutions are being found.

Case-study technology, which has become increasingly popular in recent years, has a special place in the science of criminal law. This technology is widely used in the education system of foreign countries. Since 1870, this technology has been used in the law school of Harvard University, and later it was successfully used in the business sector. Even now, the case-study technologies typical of Harvard and Manchester schools are widely used in many countries of the world. For example, 25% to 90% of the study time is taught at the University of Chicago, 30% at Columbia University, and 40% at Wharton.

With the help of case-study technologies, it is necessary to study not only one subject, but also its relationship with other subjects. In the teaching of criminal law, it is considered appropriate to use cases focused on finding a solution to the problem and making decisions.

When working with cases related to criminal law, it is necessary to aim for students to acquire analytical, practical, creative, communication, social, self-analysis skills and competencies. For this, it is appropriate to use cases with a plot, multiple subjects, a set of evidence, questions and tasks, and different sizes.

In order to apply the case-study technology, the teacher should choose a case suitable for a lecture, seminar or laboratory session and bring it to the attention of students. In this case, it is necessary to take into account aspects of criminal law's relationship with other disciplines.

When using cases, a clear and reasonable solution must be provided. Indeed, criminal law is more like specific sciences in its characteristics. Because this science does not use legal analogy or other forms of procedure. Therefore, it would not be appropriate to have several solutions in cases. Criminal cases must meet the following requirements:

- to have the complexity characteristic of typical situations related to criminal law;
- it shows the characteristics of clarification through the use of deductive methods;
- that it does not quickly lose its importance;
- able to have an educational effect on students with psychological aspects;
- serves to increase the skills of working with normative legal documents among students;
- development of students' educational-research, logical thinking skills, etc.

It is recommended to divide students into small groups to find a solution to the problem. In this way, healthy competition will be opened.

The following steps can be taken to solve the problem:

- introducing the students to the contents of the case;
- achieving full understanding of the problem by students;
- creating small groups and opening the way for their discussion;

- control of order in the auditorium, prevention of excessive noise;
- to allow students to form a case report at the end of the discussion.

The teacher can also act as a consultant or arbitrator in the processing of cases.

After the assignment is completed by the students, the presentation of the groups is prepared. When one of the group members presents it, it is necessary to allow the partners to fill it. After listening to the case solutions, the teacher can continue the discussion to find a specific solution among the diverse opinions in the small groups. Students should also be motivated by evaluating the solution of the case. A group of students who have found the correct solution and receive a positive grade (score) motivates their motivation.

As a result of active learning methods, the centralizing influence of the teacher weakens, and the activity of the audience increases. In the teaching of criminal law, consideration of complex and controversial social issues in the case-study method is one of the main ways to improve students' legal literacy. Extensive use of the case-study method in lectures and seminars plays an important role in achieving the intended purpose of the lesson.

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